

On Modeling Geotextiles by Means of Elementary Cellular Automata

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ABSTRACT

The role of cellular automata (CA) in the modeling of complex systems has been increasingly recognized over the last decades. Such modeling, on the other hand, has been focused on phenomenological approaches. Instead of dealing with the phenomena themselves, in the present paper a simple yet powerful methodology of representing the media in which a given process takes place is considered. This way, elementary CA are applied to represent the cross-section of geotextiles. The correspondence between both entities is based on three parameters, namely: the binary occupation ratio, the fractal dimension and entropy. This methodology is based on selecting a few characteristics of the media which are representative of its mean behavior. Each parameter is related to a pillar of a new kind of science which has been considered lately, namely: cellular automata, fractal geometry and chaos. An application is shown in order to validate the methodology.

KEYWORDS: Cellular automata; Binary occupation rate; Fractal dimension; Mean pore alignment parameter; Cross-section modeling.

INTRODUCTION

The study of complex media has always been of interest to geotechnical engineers. In special, being able to predict the behavior of complicated media such as soils and geotextiles shows up as a great challenge. In order to address issues related to this type of media, a new kind of science (NKS) has been increasingly taken into account. In short, NKS has three main branches, namely: chaos, fractals and cellular automata (Wolfram, 2002).

In the present paper, NKS is taken into account in order to model the cross section of a given geotextile material. The parameters which make the correspondence between the real system –

geotextile – and the idealized one – cellular automata – are chosen in order to contemplate every pillar of NKS.

In the present paper, elementary cellular automata (ECA) are used as a model of the cross-section of a given media in which any phenomena occur. Images of portions of real media are compared to the evolution of elementary cellular automata. At first, the binary occupation ratio, ζ_b , of the real image is computed. By means of comparing this value with the ones obtained from the evolution of every ECA with random initial conditions, a set of possible ECA with have approximately the same ζ_b as the image are considered. In order to choose the best candidate, two other parameters are evaluated. The entropy of the real image of the candidates ECA are evaluated and the ECA with same entropic orientation are the new candidates for models. Finally, the fractal dimension of both the real image and the ECA are evaluated, choosing the candidate which has the fractal dimension closest to the real one. This methodology is interesting as the ECA models can extended as much as desired, empowering a large scale simulation if needed.

In the next sections, each of the NKS's pillars and their corresponding characterization parameter are discussed.

ELEMENTARY CELLULAR AUTOMATA (ECA)

A complete and comprehensive study of ECA can be found in (Wolfram, 2002). The ideas behind ECA are quite simple and can be stated as follows: ECA consist of a line of cell, each colored black or white (1 or 0, respectively in a binary description). At discrete time steps a definite rule is applied and provides the color (or value) of a given cell by considering the colors (or values) of that cell and its immediate left and right neighbors on the step before (Wolfram, 2002; Ozelim et al., 2013a). Figure 1 provides a better visualization of the evolution process involved.

Figure 1: Cellular Automaton Mesh (Ozelim et al., 2013a)

ECA can, alternatively, be described by means of simple evolutions rules. In special, consider the evolution rule presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Evolution of ECA rule 30 (Wolfram, 2002, modified)

In order to better characterize ECA, Wolfram defined a numbering system. The latter considers the outputs of the transformations as coefficients in the decomposition of a given number base 2 (Wolfram, 2002). In the case of Figure 2, the rule number is given as $0 \times 2^7 + 0 \times 2^6 + 0 \times 2^5 + 1 \times 2^4 + 1 \times 2^3 + 1 \times 2^2 + 1 \times 2^1 + 0 \times 2^0 = 30$.

Cellular automata have been widely explored in science. This class of dynamical system has found application in computational fluid dynamics (CFD) as seen in the works by Hardy et al. (1973), Frisch et al. (1986), Frisch et al. (1987) and Wolfram (1986). In fact, lattice-gas cellular automata have led to the development of one of the most promising tools in CFD, the lattice Boltzmann method (McNamara & Zanetti, 1988 and Succi, 2001).

In a series of recent papers, Ozelim et al. (2013a and 2013b) showed that a new function, named iota-delta function, can be used to give quantitative interpretations of ECA. In special, by means of the iota-delta function, Ozelim et al. (2013b) show that ECA can be successfully used to model advective-dispersive phenomena. In fact, both anomalous and normal diffusion are easily treated by the latter approach (Ozelim et al., 2013b).

The applications above proposed phenomenological approaches. Only recently a few interesting papers have considered CA as models not only for the phenomena but also for the media in which the former take place (Bandman, 2010 and 2011).

In the present paper, ECA are considered as models of cross-sections of real media. In order to compare the ECA to the images of real media, three parameters have to be taken into account. The first of the, hereby defined as the binary occupancy ratio, will be discussed in the next subsection.

Binary Occupancy Ratio

Numerical experiments reveal that, starting from an initial configuration of 0s and 1s, every ECA tend to a limit density of black (numerically equivalent to 1) cells. In order to better understand this concept, consider Figure 3.

Let the binary occupancy ratio ζ_b of evolutions like the ones in Figure 3 be defined as:

$$\zeta_b = \lim_{b+w \rightarrow \infty} \frac{b}{b+w} \quad (1)$$

where, b is the number of black cells in the full evolution of the ECA and w is the number of white cells. The limit in Eq. (1) is used to show that, for a sufficiently large array of data, the value ζ_b tends to a limit. This limit is accomplished by taking sufficient steps in the evolution of a given cellular automata. In order to better visualize the concepts behind Eq. (1), let one consider Figure 4, where t denotes the number of time steps evolved.

Figure 3: ECA rules 30, 26 and 133 evolved from a random initial condition.

Figure 4: Values of the binary occupancy ratio for a few ECA rules.

Each point in Figure 4 represents the value of ζ_b obtained after the evolution of each ECA rule with initial random configuration.

It is possible to list the values of ζ_b for every ECA, making possible the comparison of any real media with ECA.

By means of the definitions given above, it is possible to proceed to the characterization of the other parameters involved in the modeling methodology. The next section will deal with chaos theory and entropy.

CHAOS THEORY

Chaos theory deals with dynamical systems which are extremely sensitive to slight changes in their initial conditions. This is sometimes called the butterfly effect.

In general, chaos is related to randomness since chaotic systems tend to be “unpredictable” due to the uncertainty in the initial conditions. In some cases, even if a chaotic system is deterministic – in the sense its governing evolution rules are deterministic – its outputs are not predictable and the only way to obtain them is by evolving the system. This is the case of elementary cellular automata rule 30 (Wolfram, 2002).

As an indicative of chaos and randomness, entropy has been a concept of interest. There are in the literature a few definitions of entropy. In the present paper, the concepts of information theory will be taken into account. This way, Shannon entropy is the parameter chosen to represent the chaotic nature of the cross-section.

Shannon Entropy

The Shannon entropy of a given random variable X is a measure of information content (MacKay, 2003). This way, this parameter can be used as an indicative of order and disorder.

Ordered media tend to have low Shannon entropy. On the other hand, chaotic – hereby interpreted as disordered – media tend to have high Shannon entropy.

Mathematically, let the Shannon entropy H_S of a given ensemble X with elements $\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x^n\}$ be defined as (MacKay, 2003):

$$H_S(X) = -\sum_{j=1}^n P(x_j) \log_2 P(x_j) \quad (2)$$

where $P(x_j)$ is the probability of appearance of the element x_j , $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$. If the ensemble X is considered a random variable, $P(x_j)$ is the probability of the event x_j . Shannon entropy is measured in bits.

In the present paper, the cross-section of the geotextiles will be treated as binary images. The conversion to binarized images is performed by means of the built-in function *Binarize* of the software *Mathematica* (Wolfram, 2014). Black pixels will be considered pores while white pixels are solids.

Being the images binary, only two elements compose the ensemble to be analyzed. This way, it is interesting to simplify Eq. (2) and define the binary Shannon entropy as (MacKay, 2003):

$$H_S^b(X) = (p_b - 1) \log_2(1 - p_b) - p_b \log_2 p_b \quad (3)$$

where p_b is the probability of appearance of black cells. Equation (3) easily follows from Eq. (2) as the elements of the ensemble X are $\{0,1\}$ and the probability of appearance of white cells is complementary to the one of black cells ($p_w = 1 - p_b$, p_w is the probability of appearance of white cells).

In order to better interpret the usage of Shannon entropy as a characterization parameter one may consider the graphical representation of Eq. (3) in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Graphical representation of Eq. (3)

A perusal of Figure 5 reveals that the maximum entropy corresponds to the situation in which the probability of appearance of black cells is 1/2. This behavior is easily explained since, if the probability of appearance of black and white cells is the same, no information about the ensemble can be stated in advance. On the other hand, when different probabilities occur, if one were to guess which value would a single element of the message take, the color with more probability would certainly be the guess to make.

In the present paper, in order to identify possible directions of ordering in the real and modelled media, Shannon entropy will be calculated in four directions, as seen on Figure 6.

Figure 6: Directions in which Shannon entropy is to be measured

By evaluating the Shannon entropy in the directions indicated in Figure 6, it is possible to ensure that possible pore alignment directions are taken into account in the modeling. The entropy is measured for each line in the images and the mean value is taken to represent each direction in Figure 6.

Following the propositions in the present paper, fractal geometry is subsequently discussed.

FRACTAL GEOMETRY

Fractal geometry has gained notoriety after the pioneer work of Mandelbrot (1982). Recently, a large number of studies have been undertaken exploring the fractal characterization of porous and fibrous media. In special, Yu and Cheng (2002) proposed a fractal in-plane permeability model for fabrics. Also, Othman et al. (2010) studied fractal permeability models for porous membranes, and Zhu et al. (2011) proposed a fractal model for coupled heat and mass transfer in porous fibrous media. Finally, Liu et al. (2011) used fractal theory to study the vertical permeability of needle-punched nonwoven geotextiles.

As the representative parameter of fractal geometry the fractal dimension has been chosen. As in the case of entropy, there are in the literature (Falconer, 2003) a number of definitions of dimension. In the present paper, the Minkowski–Bouligand – or box-counting – dimension D_b was used.

Box-counting Dimension

The box-counting dimension has been commonly used in pure and applied sciences, mainly due to the easiness inherent to its obtention and mathematical definition (Falconer, 2003). In short, its calculation is based on covering a given figure with square boxes of different side lengths ε . For a given value ε , one shall count the number of boxes which cover the figure. Let this number be $N(\varepsilon)$. This process is repeated for various lengths ε and then the data is adjusted following the equation (Falconer, 2003):

$$N(\varepsilon) = k\varepsilon^{-D_b} \quad (4)$$

where, k is a real coefficient.

One may easily check the validity of Eq. (4) for common figures. For example, consider a straight line segment with unitary length. Firstly, one shall use the box side ε_1 of exactly the length of the line. This way, the only box filled is the one in which the line segment is contained, which implies $N(\varepsilon_1) = 1$. Following this idea, by taking square boxes with length ε_2 equal to half the size of the line segment, exactly two boxes will cover the entire segment, thus, $N(\varepsilon_2) = 2$. In general, by taking boxes with side length of $1/n$, it will take exactly n boxes to cover the entire line, thus, in general, $N(1/n) = n$. The latter shows that, by means of Eq. (4), the box counting dimension is 1, as expected for a line. The same process can be repeated for 2D figures, leading to the relation $N(1/n) = n^2$, in which $D_b = 2$ as expected. A more precise mathematical formulation of box-counting dimension can be found in (Falconer, 2003).

In order to evaluate the box-counting dimension of a given figure, a computational code has been implemented in the software *Mathematica* (Wolfram, 2014). Given this brief introduction about the box-counting dimension, one shall proceed to the definition of the methodology of converting real geotextile images to ECA.

THE NKS METHODOLOGY

Consider the flow chart presented in Figure 7 as representative of the NKS methodology hereby proposed. In Figure 7, the full lines are the main path of operation.

Figure 7: Flow chart of NKS methodology.

The five steps in Figure 7 are: binarize image (1); evaluate NKS parameters (2); check for CA candidates with the closer ζ_b (3); filter CA candidates regarding directional entropy (4) and filter CA candidates regarding fractal dimension (5).

In the secondary and tertiary paths, the steps described above correspond to finding the candidate with the closest parameter to figure's one. If after step 5 the choice is not ok, then the secondary path (dashed line) is entered. Finally, in the secondary path, if after step 4 the choice is not ok, then the tertiary path (dotted line) is entered.

In order to show the applicability of the methodology hereby developed, consider Figure 8. In the latter, an image of a partially clogged geotextile (Palmeira & Gardoni, 2000 and Gardoni, 2000) and its binary form are presented.

Figure 8: (a) Image of partially clogged geotextile (Palmeira & Gardoni, 2000) and (b) its binary form.

For the binary image in Figure 8, its binary occupancy ratio is 0.40, which, by looking at Table 1, establishes as potential models rules 9, 26, 33, 37, 65 and 82.

The next step in the methodology, following Figure 7, is to evaluate the directional entropy of the real image. The results are presented in Figure 9.

Table 1: Binary occupancy ratio for every ECA.

Limits of ζ_b	Rules
0.00 – 0.03	0, 8, 32, 40, 64, 96, 128, 136, 160, 168, 192, 224
0.03 – 0.06	36, 104
0.06 – 0.10	164
0.10 – 0.13	2, 4, 1, 72, 172, 228
0.13 – 0.17	44, 100, 130, 132, 144
0.17 – 0.20	24, 66, 152, 194
0.20 – 0.24	6, 20
0.24 – 0.27	10, 12, 18, 34, 48, 68, 80, 140, 146, 196
0.27 – 0.31	38, 52, 134, 148
0.31 – 0.34	74, 88, 108, 162, 176
0.34 – 0.37	22, 35, 41, 42, 46, 49, 56, 76, 97, 98, 112, 116, 131, 138, 145, 163, 177, 200, 208
0.37 – 0.41	9, 26, 33, 37, 65, 82
0.41 – 0.44	1, 3, 5, 13, 17, 25, 67, 69, 133, 137, 141, 193, 197
0.44 – 0.48	7, 21, 39, 53, 54, 73
0.48 – 0.51	11, 14, 15, 19, 23, 28, 29, 30, 43, 45, 47, 50, 51, 55, 57, 60, 70, 71, 75, 77, 81, 84, 85, 86, 89, 90, 99, 101, 102, 105, 106, 113, 117, 120, 122, 126, 129, 135, 142, 143, 149, 150, 153, 154, 156, 157, 161, 165, 166, 169, 170, 178, 179, 180, 184, 195, 198, 199, 204, 210, 212, 213, 225, 226, 232, 240
0.51 – 0.55	27, 31, 83, 87, 109, 147
0.55 – 0.58	61, 63, 78, 79, 92, 93, 94, 95, 103, 110, 119, 124, 127
0.58 – 0.62	91, 111, 123, 125, 167, 181
0.62 – 0.65	58, 59, 62, 107, 114, 115, 118, 121, 139, 151, 171, 174, 185, 205, 209, 227, 236, 241, 244
0.65 – 0.68	173, 186, 201, 229, 242
0.68 – 0.72	155, 158, 211, 214
0.72 – 0.75	175, 182, 183, 187, 206, 207, 220, 221, 243, 245
0.75 – 0.79	159, 215
0.79 – 0.82	188, 189, 230, 231
0.82 – 0.86	190, 203, 217, 222, 246
0.86 – 0.89	191, 202, 216, 223, 237, 247
0.89 – 0.93	218
0.93 – 0.96	219, 233
0.96 – 1.00	234, 235, 238, 239, 248, 249, 250, 251, 252, 253, 254

Figure 9: Directional entropy of the real image in Figure 8 equals to: (a) 0.94 at 0° ; (b) 0.86 at 45° ; (c) 0.92 at 90° , and, (d) 0.89 at 135° .

It can be seen from both Figures 8 and 9 that the real image has a clear tendency of pore alignment in the direction of 45° with the horizontal axis. This way, the next step is to look at the orientation of the ECA candidates and then choose the new best candidates to model the cross-section.

Table 2 shows the directional entropy of the candidates.

Table 2: Directional entropy of ECA candidates.

Rules	Directional Entropy as Figure 9			
	0°	45°	90°	135°
9	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.83
26	0.96	0.39	0.96	0.95
33	0.94	0.96	0.79	0.96
37	0.96	0.96	0.77	0.96
65	0.97	0.83	0.97	0.97
82	0.96	0.96	0.96	0.40

By analyzing Table 2, it is easy to see that the remaining ECA candidates are rules 26 and 65. Finally, the next step in the NKS methodology is to evaluate the fractal dimension of the real image and the ones of the remaining candidates.

By means of a *Mathematica* (Wolfram, 2014) code, the fractal dimension of the real image is equal to 1.83 and the ones of the ECAs are both equals to 1.94. Since in this parameter there is a tie, one shall go back to the directional entropy, as the flow chart in Figure 7 suggests.

Table 2 shows that the minimum entropy is at 45° for both ECA, as expected. On the other hand, the entropy in this direction for rule 65 is much closer than the one of rule 26, thus, rule 65 is the chosen model.

Figure 10 shows a plot comparing the ECA model rule 65 and the real image. It can be seen that pore alignment is maintained. Also, ECA model tends to average the clogged spaces over the whole picture.

Figure 10: Comparison of: (a) ECA model rule 65 and, (b) real image.

ECA can be readily extended over a large domain. For example, a small sample of the geotextile can have its ECA model extended to the full real area. Since the properties studied tend to a limit as the size of the ECA increases and the modeling process is done based on the limit parameters, by evolving the ECA more steps, the extension is achieved.

Finally, ECA models can be used as backgrounds for phenomena simulation. This way, the usage of the methodology hereby proposed is fully justifiable.

CONCLUSIONS

A New Kind of Science based on cellular automata, chaos and fractal geometry has shown its value as a powerful tool in the study of complex systems. In the present paper, elementary cellular automata models for the cross-sections of geotextiles have been studied.

The methodology hereby presented is based on correlating three-parameters of a real geotextile image to the cellular automata ones. The parameters considered are the binary occupancy rate, which simulates porosity; the directional entropy, which enables one to match pore alignment directions and, finally, fractal dimension, which enables one to verify how pores are distributed in space.

By means of a small image sample of the geotextile, after the ECA model is found, it is possible to generate an image of the modelled media as big as desired since the properties of the ECA are scale independent (tend to a limit, as shown).

This way, the methodology hereby developed can be applied to model media in which numerical methods are to be applied. For example, the ECA model generated can be used as boundary conditions for lattice Boltzmann, finite elements and finite differences methods.

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